

SELF-ESTEEM OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS WITH OBESITY: EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE AND LIFE SATISFACTION

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Abstract

This research aimed to examine the relationship between social media usage, life satisfaction, and self-esteem in obese individuals. It was hypothesized that there would be negative relationship between social media usage and self-esteem and positive relationship between life satisfaction and self-esteem in obese people. It was also hypothesized that there would be gender differences in social media usage, life satisfaction and self-esteem in obese people. Correlational study with cross-sectional research design was done. A purposive sample of 200 obese individuals ($M_{age}=22$, $SD=2.25$) drawn from universities. The measure included Social Media Addiction Scale-Student Form (Sahin, 2018), Satisfaction with Life Scale (Diener et al., 1985), Body Self-esteem Scale (Mendelson et al., 1997). The result indicated that social media usage was not related to life satisfaction and self-esteem. Life satisfaction was significantly positively related to self-esteem. Social media usage and its subscales did not predict self-esteem while life satisfaction significantly and positively predicted self-esteem. There were no gender differences among social media addiction, life satisfaction and body self-esteem in obese people. This study can be useful for therapists and policy makers to develop interventions and educational programs to boost self-esteem of obese individuals.

INTRODUCTION

Social media has a significant impact on how people view themselves and their life (Febriani & Ansyah, 2023). Social networking sites frequently display user-selected versions of reality, showcasing their greatest appearances, situations, and accomplishments. As a result, regular exposure to such content may cause people to feel inadequate and compare themselves to others, which could lower their level of overall life satisfaction (Ozimek et al., 2023). In the case of obese people, who may already be subject to social stigma and a negative self-image, comparing oneself to social media ideals can

intensify unpleasant emotions and perpetuate a vicious cycle of low self-worth and negative body image (Westbury et al., 2023). It's crucial to investigate the association between social media use, life satisfaction and self-esteem, especially considering obesity. Obese people frequently have poorer self-esteem because of societal stigma and weight-based discrimination (Clark et al., 2021). Social media platforms have the potential to reinforce unfavorable opinions by emphasizing physical attractiveness and cultural ideals of beauty. Continuous exposure to pictures that promote

unrealistic body standards or admire thinness can lower one's life satisfaction and self-esteem (Aparicio-Martinez et al., 2019). People use social media platforms to communicate and share their feelings and concerns and for entertainment, searching for information and so many other reasons (Swar & Hameed, 2017). Young adults are found to be more active in social media platforms (Shannon et al., 2022). People use different social media app like Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Twitter, TikTok, and LinkedIn etc (Han & Yang, 2023).

Goffman's theory explains how people interact in social media and focus on "impression management" as on social media everyone wants to present themselves in a better way so that they do not face embarrassment. They hide their reality and present fake images of themselves so that people get influenced by them (Qi et al., 2018). According to this theory, there are three stages how someone presents himself/herself in front of others: front stage, backstage, and off stage. Front stage is the stage where one has to mask their true identity and present himself/herself according to the standards of other people. Backstage is the stage where individuals truly get to be themselves. Offstage is the stage where individuals meet other people independent of their identity they show in front of the stage (Merunkova & Slerka, 2019). Social media users hide their backstage and only show their front stage to influence others, form good impression of themselves (Sukmayadi & Yahya, 2019).

Neuropsychological research provides an understanding of why people have a desire for using social media since the brain reward circuits for self-disclosing them are as potent as the primary reward of food and sex as noted by Tamir & Mitchell (2012). Individuals are motivated to use social media for two reasons; a need to belong and a need for self-presentation. The different uses of social media involve the need to relate with other people. Social media platforms make it possible to maintain relationships with friends and families even if they are in different geographical regions. With the advancements in technology especially the internet and the constantly increasing demand for awareness by individuals in the society, social networking can be considered a basic and easily attainable way for

most people to communicate and interact (Astleitner & Schlick, 2024).

As much as social media has several benefits, its use has several effects on the individuals' health. Instead of exercising or indulging in any other form of physical activity, people could spend hours watching videos, playing games, or browsing through the different feeds on the app or site. This makes people adopt a more relaxed lifestyle and reduce energy consumption, which is likely to contribute to obesity (Kolhar et al., 2021). Social network sites usually contain pictures, cinematography as well as receipts connected to foods and rules regarding eating. While a large amount of information promotes diet and healthy eating, food commercials are widespread too, particularly those offering high-calorie, unhealthy food. The temptation that comes with seeing tantalizing images of delicious foods and drinks often leads to outrageous desires and unhealthy dietary habits that foster unmanageable desires and choices that promote weight gain and raise the risks of obesity (Filippone et al., 2022).

Life satisfaction is a complex idea that is a person's entire assessment of their life. It is a comprehensive evaluation of many areas of life, such as relationships, work, health, and personal fulfillment, among others. Fundamentally, life satisfaction measures how satisfied people are with their lives; how much they find them meaningful, satisfying, and consistent with their beliefs and goals (Bakkeli, 2021). Obesity has an impact on people's physical and mental health, interpersonal and social relationships, and overall life satisfaction which in turn touches various aspects of life satisfaction. Apart from threats to health such as chronic diseases, functional disabilities, and other complications, persons experiencing obesity stigmatization usually undergo psychological distress influenced by poor body image (Soby et al., 2023). This brings about the aspect of low self-esteem, rejection by friends and family members and feeling shameful thus makes life not so joyful. In addition, obesity is widely observed as a social disgrace resulting in poor social interactions, low social contact, and lack of social support all of which can reduce individuals' level of subjective wellbeing (Kuroki, 2016).

Self-esteem can be defined as the individual perception of overall worth or worthlessness,

capability, or worth as a person (Bailey, 2023). It is both a cognitive and emotion-based construct that describes the perceived self because of feelings, opinions, and perceptions held by a person. Self-esteem is influential in ascertaining the behaviour of individuals as well as their thinking pattern (Alsaker & Kroger, 2020). There is a multidimensional relationship between obesity and self-esteem that is influenced by social, psychological, biological, and cultural factors. Because those who are obese may internalize society's standards of beauty and thinness, obesity frequently results in negative evaluations about one's physique. Low Self-esteem and dissatisfaction are more likely to be experienced by people with high BMI due to the influence created by media and sensationalized body images (Sirola et al., 2021). Poor body image can also cause low self-esteem, embarrassment, and being self-conscious, hence having a negative impact on an individual. The self-esteem of individuals can also be affected negatively due to worry or depression that is linked to their body image and weight (Aparicio-Martinez et al., 2019).

Discrimination because of obesity can occur in the workplace, educational environments, and in other channels of social communication. Harassment in terms of bullying, discrimination, or teasing about weight affects self-image and may lead to worthlessness and social isolation and low self-esteem (Jackson, 2016). Obesity, for instance, can cause feelings of hopelessness, stress, and low self-esteem, which is very unhealthy. The available literature has evidenced a bidirectional relationship between obesity and mental health in that they are predictors of each other (Serwer & Polonsky, 2016). From the societal perception of obesity, the obese may develop low esteem, blameworthy feelings, and criticize themselves due to societal preconditioning. Such psychological consequences can also be supplemented by perceived stigma relating to weight, which results in deterioration of self-esteem (Brown et al., 2022).

Theoretical Framework

With over one-third of the world's population using social media platforms as a means of communication and sharing information, content, and ideas, social media has become a norm in the lives of man. The

Self-Discrepancy Theory postulates different self-standards that people possess those are real self, ideal self or ought self. The actual self means the qualities that people think they embedded on them, the ideal self means the qualities that people should desire to have, and ought self is the qualities people should have per the social or other people's or their norms and standards (Higgins, 1987). If obese persons are unsorted and often search for amusement through Facebook and such other social networks, reading about or watching perfect looking people and their seemingly perfect way of life can make profs feel like complete failures who would wish to be like those perfect people. By comparing themselves with such images, they may become even worse off than they were before and less satisfied with the life they lead. The purposeful snapshots provided by friends on social networks may seem even more appealing in comparison to obese patients, as they present a controlled, perfect picture of life. They themselves are already exposed to stigma and judgment regarding their size and weight and would only worsen when they try to match and compete with these perfect images of thin bodies, which will only reduce their overall self-esteem and life satisfaction.

Rationale

Obesity can be considered one of the most global health problems today and comes with various physical and psychological implications. Researchers have expressed alarm over some of the effects of the use of social media on individuals, particularly on the mental health of those who are struggling with obesity (Brown et al., 2019). Despite the previous findings, this area of studies is scarce concerning the impact of social media use on psychological factors that particularly impact health such as obesity. Concerning the psychological well-being of obese individuals, it is necessary to comprehend the effects of social media on their self-esteem and life satisfaction to enhance the intervention strategies. By evaluating the existing literature on similar topics, this study can contribute to existing body of knowledge by further clarifying the experiences of the obese people regarding social media use, life satisfaction, and self-esteem. This research will also assist in establishing if there exists a method or approach that can counter the detrimental

consequences of social media, on self-esteem and life satisfaction of obese people.

Hypotheses

- There is likely to be a negative relationship between social media usage and self-esteem in obese people.
- There is likely to be a positive relationship between life satisfaction and self-esteem in obese people.

Proposed Model

Method

Research Design

It was a correlational study with cross-sectional research design.

Sample and Sampling Strategy

The participants included in the study were 200 obese individuals. Non-probability purposive sampling strategy was used to select participants.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were:

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

- Unmarried young obese individuals with age range of 18-22 years
- Both obese men and women were included.
- Obese individuals who gained weight over time, and it has been 1 years of them being obese were selected.
- Obese individuals who have been actively using social media for the past year were selected.
- Married individuals and those with any medical conditions were not selected.

Table 1

Demographics table Showing Characteristics of Sample (N=200)

Variables	M	SD	f	%
Age	22.69	2.25		
Family income	296275	769571.93		
Gender				
Male			100	50
Female			100	50
Family system				
Nuclear			159	79.5
Joint			41	20.5
Education system				
Intermediate			8	4.0
Undergraduate			117	58.5
Graduate			62	31.0
Post graduate			13	6.5
Relationship status				
Single			134	67.0
Engaged			26	13.0
Married			24	12.0
In a relationship			16	8

Employment	Employed	52	26.0
	Unemployed	148	74.0

Assessment Measures

Demographic Sheet

The demographic sheet included age, gender, education, occupation, residential area, family system, number of siblings, and socioeconomic status.

Social Media Addiction Scale-Student Form (SMAS-SF)

This scale was developed by Sahin (2018). It is used to assess the social media addiction of youths aged between 12-22years. It comprises of 29 items on which participants have to respond on 5-point Likert scale having 1-strongly disagree and 5-strongly agree. This test has four sub-scales, Virtual tolerance, Virtual communication, Virtual problem, and Virtual Information. Social media addiction scale has good internal consistency with Cronbach alpha of .94. It subscales' Cronbach alpha is also quite satisfactory; 83 of virtual tolerance, 87 to virtual communication, 87 for virtual problem and. 81 for virtual information.

Satisfaction with Life Scale

The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) is a life satisfaction questionnaire which was formulated by Ed Diener and his coworkers in 1985. The SWLS is a very brief test composed of five items that is intended to index global cognitive evaluations of life satisfaction. To measure the respondents' agreement with each statement we have used the 7-point Likert Scale where 7 stands for 'strongly disagree' and 1 for 'strongly agree'. Internal consistency reliability of this scale is Cronbach alpha coefficient of. 87.

Body Self Esteem Scale

The body self-esteem scale (Mendelson et al., 1997) investigates how someone feels about their own appearance or body. This scale contains 23 items. Three subscales comprise the questionnaire for

adults and adolescents: BE-Weight (satisfaction about weight), BE-Attribution (evaluations others have about one's body and look), and BE-appearance (overall feelings about appearance). Respondents have to rate items on 5-point Likert scale where 0=never and 4=always. This scale had good reliability. Cronbach alpha for BE-appearance is .92, BE-weight is .94, and BE-attribution is .98.

Procedure

First, permission from the supervisor was sought to undertake this study on this topic. After that, permission was received from the authors of the scales through the email. After that, the topic was formed with the permission of the Departmental Ethical Committee. In this research, the participants were selected based on the non-probability sampling technique. Participants were briefed about research and were given the right to withdraw. They were free from deception or stress that might arise from their participation in this research. Confidentiality of the information was maintained, and the participants were ensured that their personal information would not be shared with anyone other than supervisor. They were given a consent form to give their written consent to participate in research and was followed by a demographic sheet to complete. The participants were requested to complete the questionnaire in the presence of the researcher. Every subject was provided with the legal capacity of withdrawal from the research. Once data was collected, participants were appreciated for the data collected.

Results

This study has been done to examine the relationship of Social Media Addiction, Life Satisfaction and Body Self Esteem in Obese People.

Reliability Analysis

Table 2

Psychometric Properties of the Study Variables and their Subscales (N=200)

Variable	M	SD	Range	Cronbach's α
Social Media Addiction	61.43	18.35	0-24	.89

Virtual Tolerance	11.45	4.31	10-65	.73
Virtual Communication	18.97	6.50	1-21	.78
Virtual Problem	18.17	7.39	0-34	.83
Virtual Information	13.10	4.47	0-35	.61
Life Satisfaction	22.06	6.04	11-110	.79
Body Self Esteem	51.63	11.74	0-20	.78
BE Appearance	21.01	6.46	5-35	.75
BE Weight	18.65	5.06	4-36	.59
BE Attribution	12.09	3.97	4-31	.66

Note: M= mean, SD= standard deviation, α = reliability coefficient

Correlation Analysis

To examine the relationship between demographics, study variables and their subscales, Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis was run.

Table 3
Correlation among the Demographics, Study Variables and their Subscales (N=200)

Variables	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1. Age	.22***	.01	.57***	.19**	-	.07	.16*	.12	.02	-.03	-.01	.10	.21**	.08	.19**
2. Gender	-	.17*	.11	.10	-.37***	.05	.06	.12	.14*	.06	-.15*	.10	.13	.11	.03
3. Family System	-	.05	.13	.05	.12	-.02	.09	.14	-.02	-	.01	.11	.09	.11	
4. Education System	-	.02	-.17*	.11	.06	.02	-.06	.08	-.07	.08	.11	.03	.07		
5. Relationship Status	-	-.09	-.15*	.10	.12	-.11	-.08	-.03	.12	.10	.13				
6. Employment	-	.01	.07	.02	.03	.13	.03	-.10	-.12	.06	-.08				
7. Family Income	-	.05	.05	.03	.05	-.07	-.05	.01	.05	.07					
8. Virtual Tolerance	-	.54***	.48***	.45***	-.08	-.01	.27***	.76***	.07						
9. Virtual Communication	-	.61***	.38***	-	-.15*	.37***	.82***	.20**							
10. Virtual Problem	-	.46***	-	-.22**	.34***	.83***	.09								
11. Virtual Information	-	-.12	-.08	.16*	.65**	.08									
12. BE Appearance	-	.52***	.11	-	.30***	.17*									
13. BE Weight	-	.19**	-.16*	.21**											
14. BE Attribution	-	.37**	.37**												
15. Social Media Addiction	-	.14													
16. Life Satisfaction	-														
17. Body Self Esteem	-														

Note. *.p < .05; **.p < .01; ***.p < .001

Table 3 showed the correlation among demographics, study variables and their subscales. Results showed that the age was significantly positive related to life satisfaction while all other demographic variables were not correlated with the main variables. The subscales of both variables were significantly related to each other. As far as main variables were

concerned, results showed that social media usage was not related with life satisfaction and self-esteem. However, life satisfaction is significantly positively related to self-esteem.

Regression Analysis

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was carried to find out predictors of Body Self Esteem

Table 4

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis for the Prediction of Social Media Addiction along with its Subscales and Life Satisfaction on Body Self Esteem (N=200)

Variables	B	95% C.I		S.E	β	R ²
		LL	UL			
(Constant)	42.21***	34.87	49.55	3.72		.19***
Social Media Addiction	-.05	-.49	.38	.22	-.09	
Virtual Tolerance	.67	-.04	1.37	.36	.25	
Virtual Communication	-.20	-.74	.34	.27	-.13	
Virtual Problem	-.38	-.86	.11	.25	-.24	
Virtual Information	.08	-.46	.63	.28	.03	
Life Satisfaction	.67***	.41	.92	.13	.34***	

Note. *p < .05; **p < .01; ***p < .001; Dependent variable: Body Self Esteem

Table 4 showed the predicting relationship of social media addiction along with its subscales and life satisfaction on body self-esteem. The results showed that social media addiction along with its subscales did not predict body self-esteem. However, life satisfaction positively predicted body self-esteem

suggesting the high life satisfaction was associated with high body self-esteem in obese people. The overall model was significant and had 19% of variance $F(6, 193) = 7.56 p < .001$.

Independent Sample t Test

The Independent Sample t-test was run to examine the differences in gender for study variables.

Table 5

Independent Samples t-test indicating Gender-wise Comparison in Social Media Addiction, Life Satisfaction and Body Self Esteem (N=200)

Variables	Female (n=100)		Male (n=100)		t(198)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
Social Media Addiction	59.37	18.19	63.49	18.38	-1.59	.11	.23
Life Satisfaction	21.88	5.89	22.24	6.22	-.42	.68	.06
Body Self Esteem	51.44	11.61	51.81	11.93	-.22	.82	.03

Note. M = mean; SD = standard deviation.

Table 5 indicated the gender-wise comparison in study variable. Levene's test was non-significant for all the variables. Assumptions were fulfilled. Results showed that there were no gender differences in

social media addiction, life satisfaction and body self-esteem in obese people.

Discussion

In this society, social media has become a significant aspect of life, molding the systems through which people perceive themselves in society. In this

influence, obese individuals are more affected because they have to work in environments that overwhelmingly display unrealistic beauty and body images (Shafique & Rafique, 2023). So, this study aimed to examine the relationship between social media addiction, life satisfaction, and body self-esteem of obese individuals.

Results showed that virtual tolerance was positively correlated with body esteem attribution. This is because virtual tolerance refers to a person's willingness to acknowledge different body types. If one is exposed to other body types and shapes, a person may tend to absorb such positive attitudes towards body shapes and thus evaluate his/ her body positively. This finding aligns with previous study (Jan & Ahmad, 2017). Virtual communication negatively correlated with body esteem appearance. This is because most virtual communication, especially through social media platforms, comes across beauty reflected in selected pictures which are filtered and edited. Lacking such a sense of comparison, as people compare themselves to these images, they are likely to develop feelings of rejection, shame, and dissatisfaction with their own appearance. This finding aligns with previous study (Xu et al., 2023). Virtual communication negatively correlated with body esteem weight. This is because of the constant conditioning of unrealistic beauty standards disseminated through social media and other online sites. Thus, the more people communicate in the virtual environment, the more they see images, comments, and discussions that promote thinness, or other specified body types. This comparison to designed and filtered images could cause dissatisfaction and feelings of inadequacy regarding one's own body weight. This finding aligns with previous study (Colak et al., 2023). Virtual communication positively correlated with body esteem attribution. This is because such communication allows the person to interact with positive communities, discuss body acceptance and receive support from like-minded individuals. Such positive interactions can assist people to alter the attitudes that interfere with their modelling; allow the body to be appreciated for further facets other than looks. This finding is consistent with previous study (Tassew, 2020).

Virtual problem negatively correlated with body esteem appearance. It may be because of internalization of negative feedback when individuals experience virtual problems such as cyber bullying or when they are always confronted with observations of the 'perfect' look. Such hindrances may aggravate self-doubt and criticism, which in turn, remove confidence in a specific physical appearance. This finding is consistent with previous study (Jan & Ahmad, 2017). Virtual problem negatively correlated with body esteem weight. This is because weight stigma, cyber bullying, or the intake of damaging diet culture information impairs satisfaction with body weight. If people are exposed to virtual problems such as negativity about their weight or frequently observing thin-privileged images, the former will tend to adopt those messages and increase self-criticism and virtual anxiousness for that aspect of their body. This finding aligns with previous study (Febriani & Ansyah, 2023). Virtual problem positively correlated with body esteem attribution. This is because distortions in virtual reality like cyber bullying or slender model images may have adverse effects on user's self-perception and body esteem. For instance, thin and young- attractive image on the one hand coupled with critical comments and posts made by others on social sites on the other renders people to focus onto steroids such as physical appearance attributes, self-worth and body esteem. This finding is in accordance with previous study (Pedalino & Camerini, 2022). Virtual problem negatively correlated with body self-esteem. Virtual problems refer to the matters that happen in cyber space concerning physical appearance, for example, bullying, body insulting, or advertising unrealistic and unattainable beauty standards; negative virtual-problem-body self-esteem relation happens when the virtual issues make a person lose trust in his or her physical appearance. Such virtual problems can enhance perceived inadequacy and insecure, and therefore decrease the body self-esteem. This finding is in accordance with previous study (Karim et al., 2020).

Virtual information positively correlated with body esteem attribution. This is because of awareness of positive acceptance from other people or TV advertisements, any educative content about the right body size, and shape all help in improving the

overall self-image of an individual as well as perceived body image. This finding is in accordance with previous study (Jan & Ahmad, 2017).

Life satisfaction positively correlated with and positively predicted body self-esteem. This is because people with favorable attitudes towards the appearance of their bodies tend to be happier with their lives. Body self-esteem refers to the extent to which an individual is comfortable with their body and it has a positive impact because, its impacts include, people with high body self-esteem practice better self-care, they are likely to have healthier relationship, and generally feel happier in multiple area of life. This leads to greater life satisfaction. This finding aligns with previous study (Mujtaba et al., 2022)

Among demographics age was positively correlated with BE attribution. People who are older can be more accepting of themselves and are more confident in who they are, as they get more life experiences and accomplishments that shape the overall perception of self. This finding aligns with previous study (Labeledzka et al., 2022). Age was positively correlated with life satisfaction. This is because people will have more life experiences, knowledge and psychological steadiness when they are older. These experiences can pile up over time adding to the pool of knowledge of what in fact makes a person happy. Older people may be more committed to their marriages, jobs or other forms of partnership and hence are less likely to cheat, have children, make more money, engage in volunteerism, or have a mission, and are happier. This finding is in accordance with a previous study (Bartram, 2021).

Education negatively correlated with BE appearance. It indicated that individuals with intermediate educational level had a higher level of BE appearance than postgraduates. This may stem from dissimilarities in the societal expectations and personal values and roles that are attributed to educational success. Intermediate educational levels could relate to fewer perceptions of societal and professional pressure regarding appearance, while postgraduate students may have more pressure concerned with the career and social demands that harm body image. This finding is in accordance with previous study (Shannon et al., 2023). Relationship status was negatively correlated with virtual tolerance.

It means single people had kore level of virtual tolerance. The respondents who are single may spend more time on, and interact more easily with, technology environments than those with partners who may have competed views or demands. On the other hand, people who are in a relationship might have extra social demands or expectations concerning their online activity, which may reduce their threshold for virtual problems or make them more careful. This finding aligns with previous study (Fisher et al., 2021).

There were no gender differences in social media addiction, life satisfaction, and body self-esteem. This is because both men and women go through the similar level of social networks' impact on their addiction levels. Besides, changing social roles and the distribution of resources create equal levels of happiness in life and body self-images. While there are still gender disparities in these arenas, they are not as stark as they used to be and because social media has had on young people's attitudes towards body image and health, the gap has been closed, and the experiences result in similar outcomes. This finding is in accordance with previous study (Guyen, 2019).

Conclusion

This study aimed to examine the relationship between social media addiction, life satisfaction, and body self-esteem among obese individuals. The result indicated that social media usage was not related to life satisfaction and self-esteem. Life satisfaction was significantly positively related to self-esteem. Social media usage and its subscales did not predicted self-esteem while life satisfaction significantly and positively predicted self-esteem. There were no gender differences among social media addiction, life satisfaction and body self-esteem in obese people.

Limitations and Suggestions

- There were also several methodological limitations in the present study as well as the future suggestions that are most probably to be given when carrying out empirical research. Some tools that were used in this research were in line with the western culture as they were designed.
- Scales have to be developed from the parameters accessible here, the

demographics and in accordance with the lifestyle of the obese and their mentalities.

- The study can be done on a large sample size for more generalized results
- In future, this study can be replicated by studying these variables longitudinally.

Implications

- The present study has therefore added value to indigenous literature.
- This study could be used to develop interventions including combating detrimental social media use dependency and positive enhancement of self-esteem and life satisfaction concerning obesity, and strategies to diminish adverse impacts of social networking site use.
- The study could shed light creating policies or educational programmes based on the consequences of appropriate or inadequate use of social networks and their impact on mental state, for example, obese individuals.
- It will increase awareness of the need to incorporate mental support together with obesity treatment interventions, given the influence of social media in the outlook of people.

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